

PREVALENCE OF DENTOALVEOLAR ANOMALIES IN 6-16 YEARS CHILDREN ACCORDING TO RETROSPECTIVE DATA ANALYSIS

¹ Olimov S.Sh, ² Gaffarov S.A, ³ Yakubov R.K., ⁴ Saidov A.A., ⁵ Badriddinov B.B.

Abstract. *It was studied the prevalence of dental anomalies at 6-9 years' children in Bukhara region by carried out a comparative retrospective analysis of 831 cases histories of patients with various occlusion abnormalities for 2009-2019 years. Distal occlusion and orofacial dysfunctions was diagnosed at 47,1% of all children. Number of children without orofacial dysfunctions and dentoalveolar anomalies remains almost unchanged ($p > 0,10$), whereas a share of children with dentofacial anomalies and deformities were increased from 16,5% to 72,6% ($p < 0.001$), and children with orofacial dysfunctions without of dentoalveolar anomalies signs — reduced from 66,5% to 8,4% ($p < 0.001$). Thus, orofacial dysfunctions had a high prevalence during the period of primary occlusal changes. It should be noted that one of the listed orofacial dysfunction in an isolated form was extremely rare. Most children had several dysfunctions. It follows that the correction of the orofacial dysfunctions should be carried out in an integrated manner.*

Keywords: *comparative and prevalence analysis, maxillofacial area, dentoalveolar anomalies, occlusion abnormalities, orofacial dysfunctions, children*

I. Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines oral health as the absence of diseases and disorders affecting the mouth, oral cavity and teeth. It is believed that there is a relationship between oral health and hereditary family history, since certain chronic pathologies have a greater impact on oral health, and some oral diseases cause systemic damage [25]. The health sector challenges in in different countries regardless of economic development are formidable. The Global Burden of Disease Study 2016 estimated that oral diseases affected at least 3.58 billion people worldwide, with caries of the permanent teeth being the most prevalent of all conditions assessed. Globally, it is estimated that 2.4 billion people suffer from caries of permanent teeth and 486 million children suffer from caries of primary teeth [10].

Despite of a large amount of stomatology services the dental anomalies especially between schoolchildren are still crucial point. In recent years an increase in the prevalence of oral pathology in has been observed. There were enough study results demonstrated oral health status and caries trend among children at school health surveys. Despite the fact that state governments are implementing national programs for the provision of dental care for children, however, retrospective studies in various countries of India, Australia, China, Italy, Brazil, Poland, Greece, Palestine, Jordan and others indicate the need to strengthen dental care services under public health facilities for children [4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 11, 18, 21, 22, 23, 24, 26, 27]. Some results approved disparities exist between the oral health status in urban and rural areas [4, 22, 24, 26].

II. Literature Review

¹ Tashkent institute of postgraduate medical education,

² Tashkent institute of postgraduate medical education,

³ Tashkent institute of postgraduate medical education,

⁴ Tashkent institute of postgraduate medical education,

⁵ Bukhara state medical institute

Study results of scientist group showed a statistically significant association between oral health status and hereditary family history in school children [7, 23].

Researchers in these studies reported a variety of factors at the patient, provider and system levels that influenced dental attendance. Barriers to and facilitators of parents' adherence to regular dental attendance for their children should be identified and considered when formulating health promotion policies. Further research is needed to investigate psychosocial determinants of children's adherence to regular dental visits [3, 12, 17, 19]. In fact, oral pathology is a significant public health problem over the world. Strengthening of the research in prevalence of dentoalveolar anomalies in school children by retrospective data analysis will help to provide addressing effective prevention oral health program and for managing oral diseases at school.

III. Study goal

to study the prevalence of dental anomalies at children aged 6-16 years, living in Bukhara region.

IV. Material and methods

We have been carried out a comparative retrospective analysis of 831 cases histories of patients with various occlusion abnormalities (dislocation, vertical incisive dioccluses or deep incisive occlusion) which admitted to out-patient treatment in regional dental clinic in Bukhara for 2009-2019 years.

At the same time comparative analysis patients by gender, age, labor activity, frequency of diseases occurrence in seasons, accompanying comorbidities structures and nature of conducted specialized study methods were carried out.

V. Discussion

Dentoalveolar anomalies and deformations are more prevalence stomatology pathology at school aged children. At least 75% of children and adolescents currently suffer from maxillofacial developmental disorders in the Russian Federation according to specialist assessment [6, 14]. High prevalence of the dentoalveolar anomalies (DAA) and dental caries accompanying them complications define relevance and significance of the problem of early detection and prevention of these types of pathology [1, 2].

Dental anomalies are a multifactorial pathology. There are common etiological factors: antenatal period pathology (low birth weight, pregnancy and childbirth pathology, intrauterine growth retardation), neurological status disorders; diseases of the early life period; hypodynamia; abnormal and inappropriate feeding behavior; stress and local etiological factors: bad habits, maxillofacial area (MFA) dysfunction, primary teeth removed without replaceable prosthetics and etc. [15, 16, 25]. Rajab et al (2014) reported the prevalence of caries varied significantly by sex and geographical region. In both age groups, children of the social low and middle groups had significantly higher levels of caries experience, more untreated decayed teeth and fewer filled teeth than did children of the upper socioeconomic group [21]. Other studies had reported the rural/remote children in this study had worse oral health than either state or national average in both the 5-6-year-old and 11-12-year age group. Socioeconomic status, tooth-brushing and Aboriginal status were significantly associated with caries in these communities. To close the substantial gap in oral health outcomes between rural and metropolitan residents, approaches that target rural areas, Aboriginal people and those from low socioeconomic backgrounds are needed [27]. Gavara et al. (2019) showed the prevalence of molar-incisor hypomineralization in a sample of children from Castellón between the ages of 8 and 12 years was 21.9% and only a history of perinatal hypoxia was a factor positively associated with the development of hypomineralization lesions ($p = 0.033$) [9]. Another literature searches (publication years 1996-2016) was showed that more than one billion living people have had traumatic dental injuries. World TDI frequency resulted as follows: permanent dentition prevalence 15.2% (95 CI, 13.0%-17.4%); primary dentition prevalence 22.7% (95 CI, 17.3%-28.7%); 12-year-olds prevalence 18.1% (95 CI, 15.3%-21.0%); incidence rate, 2.82 (95 CI, 2.28%-3.42%) per 100 person-years; prevalence ration, 1.43 (95 CI, 1.34%-1.52%) [13, 17, 20].

VI. Study results and discussion

As the study results were established that from 831 children with orofacial dysfunctions 39,1% of the children had a neutral occlusion in sagittal plane.

Distal occlusion was diagnosed at 391 children, which accounted for 47,1% of all children with orofacial dysfunctions. At 115 (13,8%) patients, mesial occlusion was diagnosed (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dentoalveolar anomalies prevalence analysis in sagittal plane at children aged 6-9 years with orofacial dysfunctions (n = 831)

Fig. 2. Dentoalveolar anomalies prevalence analysis in vertical plane at children aged 6-9 years with orofacial dysfunctions (n = 831)

It was revealed disorders at 86,2% of the children as an incisal disocclusion in 23,0% cases and deep incisal disocclusion in 43,2% cases in the vertical plane.

It was to be noted that children with horizontal plane disorders were excluded from the study group and were admitted to treatment to the orthodontist.

We were found that in the age of 6-7 years in 66,5% cases children have had orofacial dysfunctions without signs of dental anomalies and deformities, in 16,5% of cases, dental anomalies and deformities together with orofacial dysfunctions were detected. Number of children without orofacial dysfunctions (OFD) and DAA accounted for 17,0%.

In children aged 8-9 years was revealed the following prevalence structure of DAA and OFD: children with DAA and OFD - 72,6%, children with OFD without DAA signs - 8,4%, children without OFD and DAA - 18,9% (fig. 3).

With age in early replaceable occlusion, the number of children without OFD and DAA remains almost unchanged ($p > 0,10$), whereas a share of children with dentofacial anomalies and deformities were increased from 16,5% to 72,6% ($p < 0.001$), and children with orofacial dysfunctions without of DAA signs — reduced from 66,5% to 8,4% ($p < 0.001$) (fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Maxillofacial area anomalies and deformations prevalence at two age groups of the children (n = 831)

Thus, orofacial dysfunctions have a high prevalence during the period of primary occlusal changes. With age, as they grow older, children with orofacial dysfunctions acquire dentoalveolar anomalies associated with functional impairment of MFA, which confirms the literary data about orofacial dysfunctions as “premorbid” states of DAA at children.

A clinical examination had been revealed that 79 patients (87,8%) had not previously been observed in an orthodontist and only 11 (12,2%) were under regular medical check-up. At the same time, patients have been used removable orthodontic devices, but for various reasons the treatment was not completed.

Morphofunctional features of children and adolescents’ occlusion development of the teeth in various age periods, as a rule, impose features on frequency of occurrence of various types of disorders and pathological conditions. In our case, we have been studied a prevalence of dentoalveolar deformations depending on the period of child's occlusion development of the teeth (fig. 4).

Figure 4: Prevalence of dentoalveolar deformations among observed children depending on the period of occlusion development of the teeth

The graph shows that a prevalence of the DAA is relatively more common in late mixed occlusion than in constant (45,6%), but statistical analysis showed that difference data are unreliable ($P > 0,05$).

The structure of the DAA is dominated by occlusion pathology, which in most cases is characterized by distal occlusion (57,8%). However, it was found that distal occlusion (75,0%; $P < 0,05$) was most reliably encountered in a constant occlusion, while in a precocious mixed occlusion mesial occlusion (35,3%; $P < 0,05$) (fig.5).

In all cases, a proportional and symmetrical face has been established.

Also had a relative difference in children depending on age, so in children aged 6-9 years, a presence of prostheses of the upper and lower frontal teeth was 1,3 times more often than at the age of 13-16 years (34,9%).

Figure 5. Specific disease prevalence of the DAA depending on children occlusion formation

The central line shift to the right was observed in 5 children from 43 at 6-12 years the (11,6%), to the left - in 4 children (9,3%). At 13-18 years, the central line displacement was noted in 59,6% (28 children), while in the right and left with the same frequency (fig. 6).

Figure 6. Relationship between upper and lower center line cutters

It was revealed a lack of a place on the tooth arc of the lower jaw with retrogenia 5% of children, prognathia 61%, progenia 7% and retrognathia 27% according to gypsum models analyzes (fig. 7).

Figure 7. Gypsum models analysis in identification of excess space on the upper jaw arch among examined children

It was found that in 6 to 9 years' children, 27,8 per cent suffered from a sound-pronunciation disorder in the course of preventive examinations.

Figure 8. Prevalence data of orofacial dysfunction in children

VI. Conclusion

Various intensity degrees in respiratory disorders (from usual oral respiration to mixed breathing type) have been occurred in 62,4% of cases. A “Infantile” type of swallowing was detected in 27,4% of observed children.

It has been identified that 44,2% of children had chewing disorders, and 30,7% of children had mimic muscle para-functions (fig. 8).

It should be noted that one of the listed orofacial dysfunction in an isolated form was extremely rare. Most children had several dysfunctions. It follows that the correction of the OFD should be carried out in an integrated manner.

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